

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

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CHARACTERISTICS AND CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING WEB 2.0 SERVICES USED AT THE ENGLISH LESSONS

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Аннотация. Ақпараттық-коммуникациялық технологиялар (АКТ) саласындағы қарқынды өзгерістер оларды білім беру процесіне енгізу мүмкіндігін белсенді іздеуге ықпал етті. Қазіргі уақытта өз қызметінде тек баспа материалдарын пайдаланатын мұғалімді елестету қиын. Шет тілінде сөйлеуді үйрену процесінде негізгі орын бұл лексикалық аспектке арналған, сондықтан көптеген мұғалімдер онымен жұмыс істеу әдістерін үздіксіз жетілдіруді қамтамасыз етеді шет тілі Web 2.0 ресурстарын білім беру ортасына біріктіруге тырысады.

Түйінді сөздер: ақпараттық-коммуникациялық технологиялар, әлеуметтік қызметтер, онлайн қосымшалар, интерактивті оқыту ортасы

Annotation. Rapid changes in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT) have contributed to an active search for the possibility of their introduction into the educational process. Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine a teacher using only printed materials in his work. In the process of teaching foreign language, the key place is given to the lexical aspect, therefore, in order to ensure continuous improvement of methods and techniques of working on it, many foreign language teachers try to integrate Web 2.0 resources into the educational environment.

Key words: information and communication technologies, social services, online applications, interactive learning environment

Teaching English is no longer possible without the use of information technology. One cannot disagree with the statement of Ray Clifford, Dean of the College of Humanities at the University of Bridgeham, USA: "Computer technologies will not replace teachers, they will be replaced by those teachers who use these technologies in their practice" [1, p. 21].

The term "Web2.0" first appeared in 2004 at a conference of the O'Reilly Media publishing company, and became widely used after the publication of Tim O'Reilly's article "What Is Web2.0" in September 2005. In his article, he defines this term as "methodology designing systems that get better with an increasing number of users by taking into account network interactions" [2, p. 17].

According to Steve Lee, the advent of Web2.0 technologies has allowed "to shift the focus from technology to communication and collaboration, which in itself defines the purpose of education" [3, p. 20].

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O'Reilly himself argues that Web2.0 has no clear boundaries. Since the creator of the term and the idea himself does not consider it necessary to define its boundaries, this means that it is hardly possible to give a completely clear and precise definition of the concept.

The problem of using Web2.0 social services was actively dealt with by E. D. Patarakin, the author and coordinator of the Chronicle project. It defines the essence of social services Web2.0 as "modern tools, network software, supportive group interactions".

As E. D. Patarakin noted, Web 2.0 services arise from the bottom up due to the efforts of many independent participants [ibid.: 12]. In his article "Building a learning environment from many personal "bricks", he says that "the network ... has become a place where students are constantly, where they perform independent actions with the help of social services that help them think and act together" [4, p. 64].

Web 2.0 tools can and should not only be used in teaching a foreign language, as they allow teachers to creating learning tasks that provide instant feedback helps to create an interactive learning environment.

The formation of lexical skills involves working out such aspects of a word as its form, meaning and usage. The use of Web2.0 resources in the educational process helps to include all these aspects [5, p. 328].

Despite the variety of services and applications available, I would like to talk about the didactic capabilities of such Web2.0 services as PollEverywhere, WordWall, LearningApps, Nearpod and Quizlet. The above resources have been repeatedly used in teaching and have become very popular not only for me as a teacher, but also for my students.

PollEverywhere

Many specialists around the world already know such a service as PollEverywhere, which is not only an excellent tool for conducting surveys, voting, and analyzing student opinions during classroom classes, but a test designer to test knowledge. To work with this service, the teacher needs to create a personal account, where all created surveys will be displayed on the work screen later. PollEverywhere offers 23 types of surveys that can be created and used both independently on the site and integrated into any type of presentation (PowerPoint, Keynote or Google Slides).

When using this service, registration is required only for the creator of the surveys (in this case, for the teacher), students need to just click on the link that appears when the survey is activated and sent by the teacher, and introduce yourself. PollEverywhere is also presented as a mobile app for iOS and Android.

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The advantage of this service is that students' responses are displayed in real time. Students can complete assignments from their laptops, tablets, or phones. The survey can be organized either anonymously or with the names of the students [6, p. 140].

The possibility of conducting an anonymous survey gives shy or reluctant students the opportunity to respond freely with their classmates. All students have equal opportunities to be heard.

The basic free version of this service allows you to see no more than 25 answers to each of the questions during the running activity.

This restriction is removed in the paid tariff. As a rule, foreign language lessons are conducted in subgroups consisting of 10-13 people, so this restriction does not cause problems.

As practice shows, the PollEverywhere service is great for instant feedback and quick assessment of assimilation knowledge by students. PollEverywhere helps the teacher interactively see the full picture of students' understanding of the material they have studied, find out everyone's opinion and adjust further classes based on the data obtained.

WordWall

A relatively new website wordwall.net is a multifunctional tool for creating both interactive and printed materials. Interactive exercises can be easily reproduced on any device with Internet access: on a computer, tablet, phone or interactive whiteboard. Printed versions can be printed and used as independent assignments.

Interactive versions of games can be presented in various themes that change the appearance due to different graphics, fonts and sound.

You can also use additional options to set a timer or change the course of the game. The printed versions can also be edited. For example, there is an option to change the font or print multiple copies per page.

The 18 templates that are already presented on the Wordwall website have a very high-quality structure and allow the teacher to use them both in existing versions of the game and create their own from scratch.

If the lesson you find corresponds to the topic of the lesson, but you would like to make your own adjustments to the content, each teacher can easily customize the material according to the purpose of the lesson and the personal style of teaching. Moreover, this site provides an opportunity to switch from one template to another with one click, which significantly saves the teacher's time.

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Wordwall exercises can be used as assignments for students to complete. In this case, students are directed to this activity, without being distracted by visiting the main page. This function can be used both in the classroom, if students have access to their own devices, and as a homework assignment, after which the results of each student are recorded and provided to the teacher [7, p. 110].

LearningApps

One of the main services that modern teachers and students themselves can use in teaching is LearningApps. This service is a Web2.0 application developed as a research project of the Center of the Pedagogical College of Informatics of Education Bern in cooperation with the University of Mainz and The University of Zittau / Goerlitz.

LearningApps.org It is an interactive module designed to support learning and the teaching process. Existing modules can be directly included in the training content, as the service allows you to change them online. Users also have access to a collection of interactive blocks, which is why these blocks are not included in any programs or specific scenarios.

The teacher can choose a template for his future assignment from the available ones in the LearningApps database. In addition, all created exercises can be view in your personal account, where you can save exercises created by other teachers, which significantly saves time in the lesson [8].

Using the service LearningApps.org In language education, it can be considered in several main areas: creating your own exercises, selecting and using ready-made exercises in the educational process, organizing students' independent work by creating a virtual classroom [9].

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